

Standards and Assurance Framework for Ethical AI

SAFE AI

The Governance Gap in Humanitarian AI

Addressing the structural gap between global frameworks and operational reality

March 2026

This instalment of SAFE AI establishes five core points

1. The governance gap in humanitarian AI is structural, not addressable by individual agency policies.
2. Existing governance frameworks including the EU AI Act and NIST RMF provide important foundations but were not designed for humanitarian operational realities.
3. The central weakness is verification capacity, particularly where organisations rely on systems they cannot independently scrutinise.
4. In a resource-constrained sector, shared assurance infrastructure is needed to reduce duplication and make governance feasible in practice.
5. Uptake will depend on whether governance aligns with incentives across donors, agencies, and vendors.

SAFE AI is designed to operationalise AI governance in humanitarian contexts and sets up the foundation for independent assurance of AI deployments in high-risk humanitarian contexts. The framework releases May 2026.

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Contents

1 AI as operational infrastructure	4
AI governance is advancing, but not for humanitarian realities	5
2 Humanitarian settings expose weaknesses in AI governance	6
Pressing challenge 1: AI intensifies an existing dual-use problem related to humanitarian data	6
Pressing challenge 2: AI interaction with adversarial information environments	7
3 Why governance is the defining question	9
Infrastructure as a site of power	9
Accountability asymmetry	9
Pooled funds	10
Responsibility without control	10
Political economy of data and AI	11
Data stewardship	11
4 Participation as governance intelligence	13
Local knowledge detects what formal systems miss	13
Triangulation is essential in contested information environments	14
5 Verification for good	16
There is no consistent way to verify how these systems behave	16
Verification depends on context, not general frameworks	16
6 Operational constraints, incentives and uptake	18
Incentives determine whether good practice is adopted	18
Governance must reduce burden, not add to it	19
Shifting from using AI to using it responsibly.	19
A minimum standard is achievable now	19
7 How emerging AI systems intensify the governance gap	21
AI systems are becoming harder to see, predict, and control	21
The point of human intervention is disappearing	21
High-risk categories will require mandatory human oversight	22
What no existing frameworks yet address	22
Transparency and the right to know	23
8 Why independent assurance is needed	24
Internal governance cannot verify itself	24
Do we know how to assure models?	24
Assurance rewards responsible practice	25
Limits of upstream assurance	25
What humanitarian AI auditing involves	26
Value for money and markets signals	27
What independent assurance requires	28
Implications for humanitarian AI governance	28
9 What next?	29
Four distinct reasons to invest in independent humanitarian AI assurance	29
Bibliography	31

1 AI as operational infrastructure

Artificial intelligence is increasingly influencing operational decisions in humanitarian action, including needs analysis, prioritisation, fraud detection, operational data management, and communication with affected populations.

Yet the governance architecture required to ensure these systems operate safely, accountably, and legitimately in fragile and conflict-affected environments has not kept pace with their adoption. Humanitarian organisations are increasingly deploying powerful AI systems in contexts characterised by vulnerability, power asymmetry, and limited avenues for redress, without a sector-shared operational framework that translates global AI governance norms into safeguards appropriate for these environments.

Most global AI governance frameworks were developed with states, regulators, and technology companies in mind. They rarely translate directly into the operational realities of humanitarian organisations working in fragile and conflict-affected contexts. The result is a gap between growing expectations to govern AI responsibly and the ability to do so, particularly where organisations cannot independently verify how these systems behave in context.

The evidence base for why this matters in the AI context specifically has been building for some years. Spencer’s foundational HPN Network Papers on humanitarian AI, “The hype, the hope and the future” (2021) and “Humanitarian AI revisited” (2024), provide the most authoritative sectoral baseline for understanding how AI is changing humanitarian operations. McElhinney and Spencer (2024) make the governance argument directly. The Humanitarian Leadership Academy and Data Friendly Space’s 2025 study of 2,539 humanitarian professionals across 144 countries found that 93% of organisations were using AI tools, while fewer than one in four organisations had formal AI policies. The OCHA Centre for Humanitarian Data’s 2024 briefing note on AI and the humanitarian sector confirms the same picture at coordination system level: adoption is accelerating while governance infrastructure lags.

Independent research published in 2026 documents that algorithmic systems are entering the humanitarian space ‘mostly by the backdoor, often without safeguards’, driven by individual staff adoption rather than organisational governance and seeping into humanitarian entities’ tech stacks through updates and add-ons to existing products, with the majority of humanitarian workers relying on commercial frontier AI platforms rather than purpose-built humanitarian solutions (Coppi, 2026). Experimentation is therefore widespread, while deep integration and governance remains weak.

Many of these dynamics are emerging not from deliberate design, but from the speed at which AI capabilities are being adopted without equivalent governance infrastructure. While global attention has focused on principles and regulatory frameworks, less attention has been given to how governance is operationalised in practice. SAFE AI is an emerging approach developed to address this gap in humanitarian settings. This paper sets out the governance problem it is intended to respond to.

AI governance is advancing, but not for humanitarian realities

Across governments, standards bodies, technology companies, and ethical traditions, AI governance frameworks are rapidly emerging. These include the UNESCO Recommendation on AI Ethics, the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) AI Risk Management Framework, OECD AI Principles, and regulatory approaches such as the EU AI Act and the Council of Europe Framework Convention on Artificial Intelligence, which creates legal obligations for state parties and, by extension, the organisations they fund and partner with. Alongside these, initiatives such as the Rome Call for AI Ethics reflect the moral and social expectations shaping AI use in many humanitarian contexts, particularly where faith-based actors and community institutions play a vital role.¹

These frameworks perform different functions. Some establish normative expectations, some create legal obligations, and some offer technical guidance. Taken together, they provide a substantial foundation for responsible AI use. The challenge lies in how they are interpreted and applied in humanitarian settings, where operational conditions differ significantly from those assumed in most governance models. SAFE AI is designed to translate that emerging knowledge layer into operational governance tools for humanitarian contexts.

The UN General Assembly has now established the Independent International Scientific Panel on AI, constituted in early 2026 with a mandate to provide independent scientific assessments of AI's societal impacts which is a recognition that governance requires shared, independent knowledge infrastructure. The *Governing AI for Humanity* report, co-authored by Dame Wendy Hall among others, identifies four conditions for reaping AI's benefits while mitigating its risks: global dialogue among major AI-developing nations, an AI standards charter, a fund to support Global South participation, and a dedicated institutional home within the UN system (UN, 2025). The inaugural Global Dialogue on AI Governance convenes in Geneva in July 2026. None of these conditions has been operationalised for humanitarian deployment contexts.

The humanitarian system is simultaneously undergoing structural reform. The UN80 process is consolidating coordination, reducing clusters, and framing AI explicitly as an efficiency mechanism for a leaner system. No dedicated accountability mechanism for AI use has yet been defined within this process. The governance gap this instalment documents therefore sits within an active institutional reorganisation, rather than outside it.

1 A forthcoming SAFE AI Governance Companion will map these, April 2026.

2 Humanitarian settings expose weaknesses in AI governance

Pressing challenge 1: AI intensifies an existing dual-use problem related to humanitarian data

Humanitarian organisations are now operating within a market in which data generated through operations can carry value beyond the sector. Systems used for registration, targeting, analysis, and operational decision-making can rely on the same underlying data and model infrastructure that may also serve commercial, intelligence, or military purposes. This is now a question of access, reuse, and control over data and infrastructure.

The distinction between AI used for humanitarian purposes and AI used for military objectives is increasingly difficult to maintain, particularly in active conflict environments. AI is now embedded in contemporary armed conflict, including in systems used for planning, targeting, and operational decision-making. Data functions as a form of operational resource, in effect, as a form of “war fuel.”

There is also a national security dimension: data generated through humanitarian operations in fragile and conflict-affected states carries intelligence value that state and non-state actors have both the motive and capacity to exploit. The risks of metadata generated through humanitarian operations being exploited for purposes beyond humanitarian intent were documented before the current AI adoption wave (ICRC and Privacy International, 2018). AI intensifies those risks by increasing both the volume of data generated and the sophistication of what can be inferred from it. Local and nationally led organisations, which hold some of the most granular community-level data and have the least capacity for data protection, are particularly exposed.

A related risk operates at the model level. As humanitarian organisations move toward shared AI infrastructures and towards training models across distributed operational data from multiple agencies, those models begin to encode population-level intelligence with relevance beyond humanitarian operations. This is a particular concern when organisations open-source models for wider use.

A related practice is emerging without governance frameworks to match it. Humanitarian organisations are increasingly repurposing historical operational datasets (registration records, needs assessments, cash transfer data) to train AI models whose outputs shape future decisions. The data was collected under a service delivery mandate. Using it for predictive or anomaly detection systems constitutes a new purpose: one that affected populations could not have anticipated and could not meaningfully have refused. Research on data justice shows that identification data in humanitarian contexts is particularly prone to function creep, migration into uses that can exclude or harm the populations it describes (Martin and Taylor, 2021). The efficiency case for repurposing is real and will often be judged as worth it. But that judgement is made within institutions, without transparency to the people whose data underpins it, and without any mechanism for them to know, let alone contest, that their data has been repurposed in this way.

Humanitarian datasets are also among the most structured data available on otherwise hard-to-reach populations; as they train AI systems, they generate value beyond the

immediate use case.² That value accrues to model developers and deploying institutions. The populations whose data underpins it receive aid they were already entitled to, arguably the least fungible asset in the exchange (Martin and Tsui, 2026; Sandvik, 2023).

Purpose limitation (that data collected for one purpose should not be repurposed without fresh justification) is well established in humanitarian data protection frameworks, including the Handbook on Data Protection in Humanitarian Action (Marelli, 2025). What those frameworks do not yet address is its application to model training. When operational datasets become training material, purpose limitation does not disappear. The unresolved question is who has the authority to make that trade-off, and on whose behalf.

For humanitarian organisations, this has direct implications for neutrality, independence, and operational legitimacy. The governance architecture required to protect against these risks does not yet exist at sector level. In a sector with limited capacity for independent technical review, these risks are especially difficult to assess before systems are adopted.

Pressing challenge 2: AI interaction with adversarial information environments

In many humanitarian settings, information environments are contested and adversarial. AI systems interact with these contested information environments in ways that amplify rather than correct existing dynamics (McElhinney, 2024). These dynamics have been documented by media development and humanitarian practitioners for years.³ The IFRC's World Disasters Report 2026 now frames harmful information as a de facto humanitarian crisis at the level of the sector's most authoritative annual publication confirming what operational actors including CDAC Network, ICRC, MSF, and UNHCR had already established through their work in conflict and crisis contexts (IFRC, 2026).

Governance needs to address not only whether outputs are technically accurate, but how they are likely to function within such a contested information ecosystem. They interact with existing dynamics of misinformation, distrust, manipulation, and limited means of verification. Trust in institutions is often fragile, and communities may have limited ability to verify or contest the information they receive. From the perspective of affected populations, the harm caused by an AI-generated error, coordinated inauthentic behaviour, or deliberate disinformation may be indistinguishable.

These risks are not evenly distributed. Women and girls are disproportionately affected by harmful information environments, including targeted disinformation, harassment, and exclusion from access to accurate information. When AI systems amplify these dynamics through inaccurate outputs, mistranslation, or context-blind responses, the consequences can be severe, particularly in contexts where access to services, protection, or rights is already constrained.

2 In January 2026, SpaceX updated Starlink's privacy policy to permit the company and third-party partners to collect user and communication data to train artificial intelligence models. Starlink is increasingly used by humanitarian organisations to deliver connectivity to crisis-affected populations. The update was made unilaterally, without consultation with humanitarian users, and illustrates how operational data generated through humanitarian service delivery can become training material for commercial AI systems under terms set entirely by the provider. See Martin and Tsui (2026) for discussion of the governance implications.

3 Actors such as IMS, DW Akademie, Fondation Hirondelle, BBC Media Action and Internews have made significant contributions on understanding trends in information integrity in crisis. See for example *Sudan's information war: How weaponised online narratives shape the humanitarian crisis and response* (CDAC Network, 2025).

Existing AI governance frameworks were not designed for contexts where the information environment is adversarial and manipulated, where technical infrastructure is contested, and the boundary between civilian and military use is unstable. This is central to AI governance considerations in humanitarian action, particularly in conflict and crises.

The cost of the governance gap is not theoretical. Documented incidents, including a sophisticated cyberattack against systems holding sensitive data on hundreds of thousands of vulnerable people, the sharing of refugee data without informed consent, and disputes over biometric systems linked to the suspension of food aid, are just a few of the well-known recent examples that illustrate what weak oversight, inadequate procurement controls, and insufficient community safeguards produce in practice.⁴ These are the predictable consequences of deploying technologies in high-stakes environments without proportionate governance. These patterns are reflected in global tracking efforts such as the *OECD AI Incidents Monitor* and the *AI Incident Database*, which document similar failures across other sectors.

The documented harms do not exhaust the risk. Humanitarian organisations are deploying AI systems before the sector understands their full societal consequences – a pattern the adoption of social media established, with effects we are still managing.

4 ICRC cyberattack (2022): data on 515,000 people compromised. UN sharing of Rohingya biometric data without informed consent (reported Human Rights Watch, 2021). Biometric system disputes linked to food aid suspension in Yemen (Devex, 2019). These incidents, which are indicative not exhaustive, are cited in full in the references section.

3 Why governance is the defining question

Infrastructure as a site of power

Humanitarian reform has traditionally been framed in terms of mandates, funding, and institutional change. But a deeper transformation is already underway. As AI becomes embedded in the digital infrastructure through which aid is delivered, power and humanitarian legitimacy increasingly sit at the infrastructure level.

System design now determines who is visible, who qualifies, who is flagged, who is excluded. This is not a new accountability failure as humanitarian systems have always made decisions that excluded people without adequate redress. What AI changes is the scale at which those decisions operate, the opacity that makes them structurally resistant to explanation, and the lock-in that makes correction dependent on actors outside the sector's control.

When those decisions cannot be explained or contested, impartiality weakens. When data flows are governed elsewhere, independence narrows. When there is no route to redress, humanity becomes conditional. The humanitarian principles that define this sector's legitimacy are not immune to the governance choices embedded in the systems we deploy. This mirrors wider debates on digital public infrastructure, where control over foundational systems shapes access, inclusion, and accountability.

This is not a theoretical risk at the margins of humanitarian practice. This applies not only to high-risk systems such as eligibility determination or biometric identification, but more insidiously to everyday applications including translation, information provision, triage, and workflow automation, where cumulative effects shape how aid is understood, accessed, and experienced. It also increasingly includes shared or externally provided AI infrastructures that may be adopted across multiple organisations. Decisions embedded in these systems can therefore extend beyond a single deployment, shaping operational outcomes across the wider system.

Accountability asymmetry

The humanitarian sector is structurally more accountable to donors than to affected populations. AI systems risk further entrenching this imbalance, as decisions may be shaped by systems that are not transparent to those they affect and not meaningfully contestable. Humanitarian organisations are responsible for the outcomes of AI systems they do not fully design, control, or understand. At the same time, affected populations have limited knowledge of these systems, and limited ability to contest or seek redress for decisions that shape their access to assistance and protection. These dynamics also have differentiated impacts. Where governance systems are weak or opaque, those already facing barriers to access and participation, including women and girls, are more likely to experience exclusion, misclassification, or harm without meaningful routes to remedy.

This asymmetry is not new. Research on communication technologies in humanitarian aid has documented that accountability mechanisms consistently reproduce the appearance of responsiveness without redistributing decision-making power to affected populations (Madianou et al., 2016). AI systems inherit and intensify this dynamic.

Organisations that depend on community trust for access cannot afford to treat governance infrastructure as optional. These pressures are intensified where organisations are being asked to adopt AI in the name of poorly defined efficiency expectations, while lacking the time, leverage, or technical capacity to scrutinise the systems they are using.

Pooled funds

This dynamic is reinforced through the structure of humanitarian financing. Pooled and pass-through funding mechanisms are among the most direct investments in operational delivery and affected communities and are correspondingly closest to where AI systems are experienced. But these mechanisms were not designed to carry AI governance requirements and are uniquely under-equipped to make determinations about the systems they now enable. The result is a structural gap: the funding closest to affected people is the least likely to have accountability mechanisms attached to the AI it funds. This is one reason the resource context matters. The parts of the system closest to delivery are often the least resourced to assess technical risk. Without shared governance infrastructure, the efficiency case for AI can end up shifting cost and accountability onto the actors least able to absorb them, a strong signal for an area that should be prioritised.

Responsibility without control

Humanitarian organisations are increasingly using AI systems that they did not build and cannot fully inspect. Many of these systems rely on proprietary models, external platforms, or third-party tools where the underlying logic, training data, and system behaviour are not fully visible to those deploying them.

Research into the relationship between humanitarian actors and technology providers found that companies were largely unwilling to disclose the terms of their agreements with humanitarian organisations, and that the sector's dependence on a small number of dominant infrastructure providers, including near-monopoly concentration in cloud computing, has created structural asymmetries procurement processes have not been designed to address (Coppi, 2024).

This creates a disconnect between responsibility and control. Organisations remain accountable for decisions influenced by these systems, including decisions affecting access to assistance, prioritisation, and protection risk. At the same time, they often lack the ability to independently assess how those systems function, how outputs are generated, or how they may behave under different conditions. Access to technical documentation, model architecture, and training data is frequently limited. Even where information is available, organisations may not have the capacity to interpret or test it in practice. System behaviour can also change over time through updates, retraining, or interaction with new data, further reducing visibility over how decisions are being shaped.

The result is a form of responsibility without control. Organisations are expected to govern systems whose behaviour they cannot fully observe, test, or explain. This creates a limit to what internal governance processes can achieve on their own.

This constraint is not resolved through procurement alone. Contractual terms can improve transparency and establish audit rights, but they do not in themselves provide the means to evaluate complex systems or to test how they perform in specific operational contexts. A 2025 report to the Human Rights Council by the UN Working Group on Business and Human Rights identifies systematic gaps in legislative frameworks for rights-respecting AI procurement as one of the most significant unresolved governance challenges – a finding that applies with particular force to humanitarian procurement contexts where accountability to affected populations is weakest (UN Working Group, 2025).

In practice, organisations are often required to rely on assurances provided by vendors, without the ability to independently verify them. Access Now's [new work on AI procurement in humanitarian settings](#) along with SAFE AI's procurement guidance, examines what contractual protections are available and where gaps persist, and points to this as one of the most actionable near-term levers available to the sector.

Political economy of data and AI

Related to the dual use challenge, a broader shift has taken place in the political economy of data and AI. Data and insights generated in humanitarian contexts may contribute to systems used far beyond those contexts, including in commercial and security applications. Value accrues upstream to those controlling models and infrastructure, while risks and accountability remain downstream with implementing organisations and affected populations. Sandvik's analysis of humanitarian extractivism establishes that this is not a new dynamic introduced by AI but a structural feature of digital transformation in aid that AI intensifies (Sandvik, 2023; Madianou, 2019). Sandvik (2024) argues that framing humanitarian AI primarily as an ethics question obscures the structural and political dimensions of who controls AI infrastructure and who bears its risks – a distinction this paper attempts to maintain throughout.

The data that powers humanitarian AI systems is generated through the interactions of affected communities with humanitarian services, including registration, needs assessment, cash distribution, and protection processes. As AI systems are developed and deployed, this data contributes to model training, algorithm refinement, and the generation of insights that extend beyond the immediate humanitarian context.

This introduces a further challenge. While AI is often framed as a means of improving efficiency and effectiveness in humanitarian delivery, the distribution of value generated through these systems is less clearly defined. Value may accrue to providers and infrastructure owners who process this data, while the communities whose interactions generate it may not share in those benefits. The labour costs embedded in these systems follow the same asymmetry. The workers who make AI systems operational, including content moderation and data labelling in low-income countries, are rarely visible in governance discussions, and rarely protected by them (UNDP, 2025; TIME, 2023; Bender et al., 2021).

As shared AI infrastructures begin to emerge across the humanitarian system, these dynamics become more pronounced. Model design choices, data governance decisions, and system architectures established by a small number of actors may shape how AI operates across multiple organisations. This creates system-level dependencies in which individual agencies rely on infrastructures they have limited ability to scrutinise, adapt, or contest.

All of this is increasingly shaped by the rise of sovereign AI strategies, where states are investing in domestic control over data, models, and compute infrastructure for economic and security reasons. While these developments are not specific to the humanitarian sector, they influence the environments in which humanitarian organisations operate. Systems and infrastructures used in humanitarian contexts may be governed by national priorities that do not align with humanitarian principles, further complicating questions of control, access, and accountability.

Data stewardship

The sector has begun to name this problem. The IASC Humanitarian Data Collaborative, established by IASC Principals in October 2025, identifies a governance pattern in which decision-making power is concentrated with large global actors, while local organisations and affected communities are positioned primarily as data providers. Its work includes

developing approaches to data ownership, access control, and benefit-sharing, and signals a shift towards models that treat data as something collected with and for people, rather than about them. This direction is important, but not yet operationalised at scale.

Parallel work outside the humanitarian sector points in a similar direction. Emerging approaches to data stewardship and collective governance demonstrate that decisions about access, use, and benefit-sharing can be structured to retain value within the communities from which data originates (see, for example, Verhulst and Young, 2017; Delacroix and Lawrence, 2019; Delacroix et al., 2020; Viljoen, 2021). A broader framework for understanding data governance as a justice question rather than only a technical one is developed in Taylor (2017). These approaches remain early, but they indicate that alternative models are possible.

For humanitarian AI, this raises a practical question of how governance frameworks can ensure that value derived from data is aligned with humanitarian objectives and does not reinforce existing asymmetries of power and benefit. Approaches such as SAFE AI include provisions in procurement and data governance to support greater transparency, control, and accountability in how data is used and shared. Realising this in practice depends on mechanisms that can make these commitments credible.

This dynamic also connects to the sector's broader resource constraints. Where value accrues upstream to model and infrastructure providers, while governance costs sit downstream with implementing organisations, the system becomes harder to sustain for the organisations closest to affected populations.

4 Participation as governance intelligence

Local knowledge detects what formal systems miss

Participation is often framed as a question of inclusion or legitimacy. In the context of AI governance, it also performs a more practical function. It is a source of information about how systems behave in specific operational contexts.

This aligns with a growing body of work on participatory AI, which treats affected populations not only as users or beneficiaries, but as contributors to how systems are evaluated, governed, and adapted in practice. This includes approaches emerging from research and practice on participatory machine learning, community-based auditing, and data stewardship. The argument that those most affected by design decisions should shape them is developed most fully in Costanza-Chock (2020), whose design justice framework provides the governance principles applicable here. Delacroix and Lawrence (2019) extend this to data specifically, proposing bottom-up governance models in which communities hold representational authority over data decisions rather than advisory roles.

Emerging participatory auditing methodologies, including the PHAWM framework developed by a UK academic consortium with EPSRC funding, are beginning to establish the community-centred audit practice as an expected standard in domestic AI governance contexts. SAFE AI would propose that principle be explored in humanitarian deployment conditions where the governance stakes are categorically higher and the tools must be built for the context, not adapted from it. In these conditions, participation is not only a question of inclusion. It is part of the governance infrastructure required to understand and manage how systems behave in practice.

AI systems do not operate in abstract environments. Their outputs are shaped by language, data quality, cultural context, and how they are used in practice. They function as sociotechnical systems, shaped as much by context, use, and interaction as by model design. These are conditions that cannot be fully captured through technical testing or upstream model evaluation. They are experienced in use, often first by the communities interacting with the system.

The argument that AI systems reflect the social and historical conditions of their training data and that this makes community accountability a technical governance requirement, not a values aspiration was made directly in the humanitarian context at CDAC Network's 2024 event convened around the question of whether the sector needs a humanitarian manifesto for AI (Birhane, 2024).

No vendor audit, no internal review process, and no documentation requirement can fully substitute for structured input from the people who stand to gain and will live with the consequences of deployment decisions.

CDAC Network's co-design work with refugee communities in Kakuma has demonstrated how affected populations can meaningfully engage with questions of AI use and governance, including identifying risks, expectations, and acceptable use conditions including analysis of "participation washing" risks, where engagement does not translate into influence over system design or use (Madianou, 2019).

The testimonies gathered in Kakuma and Kalobeyei Settlement, brought directly into policy discussions through film made by FilmAid Kenya and screened at an FCDO-convened Wilton Park gathering in May 2024, constitute the only direct evidence in this paper from people whose lives are shaped by the AI systems this governance framework addresses. That methodological fact is itself a governance argument: the absence of community voice from most AI governance reflects the same accountability asymmetry this paper documents throughout (FilmAid Kenya and CDAC Network, 2024).

Triangulation is essential in contested information environments

Emerging evidence from humanitarian practice shows that affected populations can identify issues that are not visible through system-level assessment alone. These include misinterpretation in local languages and slang, exclusion errors, and unintended effects on how assistance is accessed. In Sudan, for example, our efforts to detect coordinated inauthentic behaviour online have combined AI-based detection analysis with technical partner Valent combined with validation from local information champions. This triangulation has made it possible to identify patterns that automated systems alone would misinterpret or miss entirely, demonstrating how community input can improve both accuracy and contextual understanding.

This points to a limit in how governance is often approached. Participation is sometimes reduced to consultation, where communities are asked for feedback, often late in a process, but have limited influence over how systems are designed or used. This creates a risk of participation washing, where the appearance of engagement does not translate into meaningful input into governance decisions (Madianou, 2019).

For participation to function as governance, it needs to be connected to decision-making and system design. This includes how systems are selected, how risks are assessed, and how outputs are used in practice. It also requires that feedback from communities can influence whether systems are adjusted, limited, or withdrawn.

This enhances technical governance. Participation provides a form of real-world feedback that cannot be generated through internal processes alone. It is one of the few ways to observe how AI systems behave in the conditions in which they are actually used.

Operational models for participatory governance including citizen juries, data trusts, and community governance boards are developed in the Ada Lovelace Institute's work on participatory data stewardship (Ada Lovelace Institute, 2021). Connected by Data principles for public participation in AI procurement (2025) also provide a practical governance model for community participation in procurement decisions. Both provide practical architectures for the principles this section articulates.

Participation in this context extends beyond consultation or feedback mechanisms. It includes the role of locally based technical actors – developers, data practitioners, and institutions in crisis-affected regions – in shaping how AI systems are designed, adapted, and governed. Humanitarian AI systems are frequently developed in Global North contexts and deployed elsewhere, carrying embedded assumptions about language, behaviour, and decision-making that reflect the data environments in which they were built rather than the societies in which they operate. These misalignments are a recurrent source of system failure producing outputs that misclassify, exclude, or do not reflect lived realities precisely because the knowledge required to avoid those failures was absent from the design process (Raji et al., 2021).

Recognising and integrating AI capability in the Global South delivers system validity. Where local technical expertise is excluded from or absent from design and governance processes, systems are more likely to fail the populations they are meant to serve. Governance frameworks that treat participation as consultation after design miss an upstream dependency that determines whether systems work at all. Effective governance requires that those with contextual knowledge to be involved in shaping systems, not only in assessing them after deployment (Costanza-Chock, 2020)

5 Verification for good

There is no consistent way to verify how these systems behave

A pervasive finding across AI governance work is that monitoring and verification are use-case specific. General frameworks can establish principles and expectations, but they cannot determine in advance what needs to be checked, by whom, and at what threshold in every operational context.

This is reflected in NIST's March 2026 report, *Challenges to the Monitoring of Deployed AI Systems*, which draws on global expert input to show that monitoring requirements vary by sector and deployment context. General frameworks cannot prescribe what to monitor or how to assess system behaviour in settings they were not designed for.

This is a pattern across AI governance. Normative frameworks arrive first. The implementation architecture needed to operationalise them follows later, sometimes years later. The gap between them is a transition period. It is also the period in which harm will certainly occur. The UN's own *Model Policy on the Responsible Use of AI in UN System Organizations*, formally adopted in 2024, establishes risk classification, accountability structures, and lifecycle oversight obligations across the UN system. It does not provide the sector-specific tooling, or independent verification infrastructure needed to meet those obligations in humanitarian deployment conditions. SAFE AI is proposing architecture be built now, before the gap closes on its own over an uncertain timeframe, precisely because waiting for norms to stabilise before investing generates the most preventable harm.

Verification depends on context, not general frameworks

Humanitarian operations represent conditions where this gap is particularly acute. They are characterised by power asymmetry between organisations and affected populations, adversarial information environments, limited connectivity, and weak or absent legal recourse. In these contexts, the limits of general-purpose governance approaches become most visible.

Verification changes what governance needs to look like at the sector level. There is currently no shared mechanism within the humanitarian sector for independently verifying how AI systems behave in practice or for assessing whether governance claims hold in specific operational settings. The OCHA Centre for Humanitarian Data's peer review framework for predictive analytics established that independent review of methodology is required before deployment in humanitarian contexts (OCHA, 2021) but has not extended that principle to AI systems more broadly.

This is compounded by well-documented problems in the datasets on which AI systems are trained. Raji et al. (2021) survey the development and use of datasets in machine learning research, finding systematic gaps in documentation, representativeness, and accountability that make independent verification of system behaviour structurally difficult, particularly for populations underrepresented in training data.

This becomes even more acute as shared infrastructures are adopted across agencies. Where multiple organisations depend on common models or platforms, the ability of any one actor to independently verify how those systems function is further reduced.

The ICRC's 2024 AI Policy represents the most developed agency-level AI governance framework in the humanitarian sector. It establishes risk classification, accountability structures, and operational commitments that go well beyond principles. It is also honest about its limits. Governance at the agency level however rigorous cannot independently verify its own claims, cannot provide assurance to external partners and donors, and cannot resolve the accountability gap that arises when systems are procured from vendors whose architecture is not fully visible to those deploying them. If the sector's most governance-capable organisation cannot close that gap alone, the gap is structural. It also requires infrastructure that operates above the agency level, independent of any single organisation.

Where verification cannot be performed internally, it must be provided independently. This is the shift from governance as process to governance as assurance.

What SAFE AI is and what it is not

One response to this set of constraints is SAFE AI. SAFE AI is governance infrastructure for AI deployments in humanitarian contexts. By providing proportionate, risk-based governance, SAFE AI enables faster and more confident deployment of AI systems, reducing uncertainty and avoiding delays and costs caused by unmanaged risk. SAFE AI provides:

- a governance architecture to translate global AI norms into operational tools
- a risk-tiered framework for humanitarian AI use cases
- actionable controls across procurement, deployment, monitoring, and accountability
- the foundation for independent assurance of high-risk deployments

SAFE AI is not:

- a voluntary ethical code
- a single organisation's internal policy
- a technology platform or software product
- a mandatory regulatory regime
- a substitute for legal or regulatory compliance
- a substitute for independent critical thinking

Humanitarian quality standards such as CHS and Sphere define what good practice looks like. SAFE AI is concerned about how claims about those practices are upheld and made verifiable in the context of AI systems.

Existing frameworks provide important principles, obligations, and technical guidance, but they do not on their own provide a complete operational model for humanitarian deployment conditions. Without it, humanitarian organisations cannot meet emerging governance expectations. This matters particularly in a constrained operating environment. Organisations need something that can be integrated into existing procurement, programme design, oversight, and review, while reducing duplication across teams and agencies.

Adoption support and assurance infrastructure are distinct functions. Existing initiatives such as NetHope (2024) play a critical role in strengthening adoption and digital capacity across the sector. SAFE AI addresses assurance infrastructure required to independently verify how AI systems behave once in use.

6 Operational constraints, incentives and uptake

Any governance approach in the humanitarian sector has to work within existing operational constraints. Teams are under pressure to deliver quickly, often with limited technical capacity and increasing reporting requirements. This is consistent with findings from practitioner networks such as MERL Tech which show widespread experimentation with AI alongside limited institutional capacity for governance, particularly in monitoring, evaluation, and learning functions. Humanitarian organisations are also operating under ever tighter financial and staffing constraints following funding reductions, while expectations around accountability and delivery continue to rise. The urgency of establishing sector-wide minimum standards before widespread adoption forecloses the option is developed in McElhinney and Spencer (2024), and the risks of AI adoption driven by efficiency pressure rather than considered governance are examined in Spencer et al. (2025).

Fragmentation across organisations compounds this challenge. Where governance is developed independently, similar assessments, documentation, and review processes are repeated across agencies with limited coordination. This adds cost, slows decision-making, and places additional burden on already stretched teams. In the absence of shared infrastructure, governance risks becoming duplicative rather than enabling.

Incentives determine whether good practice is adopted

The main barrier to stronger AI governance is how it fits with existing incentives and structures. Donors are often looking for visible results and innovation. Vendors are focused on uptake and scale. Governance, by contrast, is often seen as slowing things down or adding cost without immediate benefit. Under these conditions, even well-designed approaches are likely to face resistance unless they are clearly linked to operational value. The mechanisms that work are conditionality, donor requirements that make compliance a prerequisite for access to humanitarian procurement, and independent assurance that makes governance claims verifiable regardless of vendor preference.

Adoption is shaped as much by behaviour as by design. Early uptake by teams is more likely where governance supports judgement rather than policing it, and where it helps reduce uncertainty rather than adding process, but be aware that shifting incentives is necessary but not sufficient. The humanitarian sector currently relies on ethics charters, voluntary commitments, and codes of conduct as its primary governance mechanism. Research on AI procurement has characterised this approach as regulatory hallucination: the appearance of oversight without the legal framework that gives it substance (Sanchez-Graells, A. (2024) cited in Coppi (2026)).

In other sectors, culture change has happened when better practice becomes easier than weaker practice. The same principle applies here, even against a backdrop of turbulence and funding cuts. Humanitarian professionals who build governance into their practice now, and who demonstrate that responsible AI adoption is operationally credible, not just ethically desirable, are defining what good leadership looks like.

Governance must reduce burden, not add to it

Workable governance fits into what organisations are already doing. That means aligning with procurement processes, programme design stages, and existing accountability systems. It should be proportionate, so that lower-risk uses do not absorb the same level of attention as high-risk ones. A tiered approach allows organisations to focus effort where it is most needed, while keeping lighter-touch processes for routine use cases.

Donor requirements remain one of the strongest levers in the system. Where expectations around AI governance are clear and consistent across funding streams, organisations are far more likely to adopt them. Provision of access to shared assurance support can stem the digital governance divide before it hardens, rather than trying to reopen it later. Smaller actors in particular are unlikely to build internal capacity for technical assurance. Access to external review or pooled mechanisms makes participation more feasible.

Shifting from using AI to using it responsibly.

One further barrier is rarely named. There is currently no requirement to report AI failures in humanitarian contexts and no institutional incentive to do so. Organisations that surface problems risk reputational damage and those that stay quiet accumulate risk invisibly. Without a structured record of what goes wrong, and why, the evidence base for improving governance cannot develop. Aviation became dramatically safer because reporting failures became normal and lessons were shared. The humanitarian sector needs the equivalent: a mechanism for logging AI incidents and near-misses, and aggregating them across organisations. Without it, governance remains reactive to failures rather than anticipating and preventing them.

At present, adoption is often rewarded more than the quality of governance behind it. What would help is the creation of visible incentives for good practice, including public recognition, budget lines for responsible governance practices, and lighter-touch reviews for those with strong AI governance. Finally, early approaches should support organisations to improve, not only assess them. If governance is experienced primarily as compliance, uptake will be limited. If it helps teams make better decisions with less uncertainty, it becomes useful.

A minimum standard is achievable now

SAFE AI's risk-tiered architecture is designed for this reality. Tier 1 requirements, for example, are achievable without specialist capacity, allowing smaller and locally led organisations, which are often closest to affected communities and furthest from governance support, to engage.

The minimum standard organisations should adopt now, regardless of capacity, is this:

1. Appoint a single point of contact for each AI deployment (who is speaking with the various people in the team required to safely deploy AI).
2. Maintain documentation that allows an independent reviewer to follow the decision trail without additional explanation.
3. Record and justify departures from agreed governance processes, rather than leaving them unaddressed, and continue to monitor.

This is the difference between governance that can be demonstrated and governance that can only be asserted.

This is also the operational foundation for something more fundamental. Crisis-affected communities have a right to know when AI materially influences decisions that affect their access to aid, and a right to contest those decisions. That right is only meaningful if the governance trail exists to support it. Documentation standards, named accountability, and externally reviewable decisions are practical means through which this becomes real. The credibility of humanitarian AI will be tested by whether decisions can be scrutinised, contested, and, where necessary, corrected.

However, even under the best conditions, it is not realistic to expect overstretched humanitarian organisations to carry the full burden of responsibly governing AI. That burden needs to be shared, particularly as the governance gap is about to accelerate.

7 How emerging AI systems intensify the governance gap

AI systems are becoming harder to see, predict, and control

Recent developments in generative, agentic, and frontier AI systems are changing the conditions under which governance operates. Generative systems reshape how information is produced and interpreted. Agentic systems reshape how decisions are enacted. Frontier models concentrate capability and influence in the infrastructures on which these systems depend. Frontier models also introduce capabilities whose failure modes are not fully understood in advance, increasing uncertainty at the point of deployment. The International AI Safety Report 2026 identifies mitigation of frontier model risks as among the most active areas of current international effort and among the least resolved (International Safety Report, 2026). The call for adaptive, proactive governance to manage extreme AI risks, including both technical research and institutional development, has been made explicitly by some of the field's most authoritative voices (Bengio et al., 2023)

This is not a new concern. Bender et al. (2021) established that large language models produce outputs whose relationship to underlying data is opaque even to their developers, with risks that are context-dependent and resistant to pre-deployment identification – conditions that apply with particular force in humanitarian deployment settings. Together, these developments intensify the governance gap identified above.

The governance landscape described so far was developed for earlier forms of predictive AI, where inputs were known and outputs were reviewed by humans before action was taken. That assumption is no longer holding.

The point of human intervention is disappearing

In earlier AI systems, the governance window sits between output and action. A human reviews a recommendation and decides whether to act. In agentic systems, that window collapses. Systems sequence their own actions, retrieving data, generating outputs, and triggering workflows as part of a continuous chain. By the time a human becomes aware of what has happened, the consequences may already be in place. The effect is a compression of governance intervention points. Oversight shifts earlier, into system design and configuration, rather than at the point of decision.

The effect is a shift in risk from prediction errors to errors in information, action, and interaction.

Agentic systems pursue goals across multiple steps, invoke tools, and take actions with varying degrees of autonomy. This introduces risks in how decisions are sequenced and enacted, often with limited opportunity for intervention once a process has begun.

Generative systems, which create and synthesise content across text, image, audio, and video, are also being widely used to support decision-making and communication. This introduces risks in how information is created, translated, and communicated, particularly in low-resource languages and high-stakes contexts.

High-risk categories will require mandatory human oversight

SAFE AI's risk-tiering approach applies to these systems, but certain categories of agentic capability require explicit treatment as high-risk.

- **Autonomous eligibility and targeting decisions**
Systems that determine or update who receives assistance without human review before action is taken. Where the consequence of error is exclusion from aid, meaningful human oversight is non-negotiable.
- **Agentic access to sensitive data at scale**
Systems capable of retrieving, aggregating, or transmitting beneficiary data across systems without per-action authorisation. Risks include not only data breach, but new forms of profiling or re-identification created through automated aggregation.
- **Community-facing autonomous communication in adversarial environments**
Systems interacting directly with affected populations without clear disclosure, escalation pathways, or quality control. In contexts of dependency and limited alternatives, the consequences of misinformation can be severe and irreversible.

These risks do not occur in isolation. They interact with existing operational conditions, including adversarial information environments, low trust, and limited means of verification. In these contexts, errors may not be distinguishable from manipulation, and their cumulative effects may not be traceable to a single system or decision point.

What no existing frameworks yet address

Most current AI governance frameworks and standards, including ISO/IEC 42001, the NIST AI RMF, and the EU AI Act, were developed before generative and agentic systems became widely integrated into operational workflows.⁵ They provide strong foundations for lifecycle governance, risk classification, and documentation.

They do not yet adequately address:

- governance at the level of action rather than system
- multi-model, multi-step architectures
- attribution of responsibility across automated decision chains

They also do not fully account for the concentration of capability and influence associated with frontier models, where governance depends not only on how systems are used, but on infrastructures that shape outcomes across multiple organisations and that humanitarian actors have limited ability to scrutinise, influence, or hold to account.

Existing humanitarian guidance, including the IASC Data Responsibility Guidelines and UN human rights due diligence frameworks, provide important anchors. But applying these principles to these systems requires governance at the level of system behaviour and interaction, not only at the level of system design.

⁵ The most technically authoritative guidance on generative AI risk is NIST AI 600-1 Generative AI Profile (2024).

Transparency and the right to know

A minimum baseline emerging across AI governance discussions is a right to know whether and how AI systems are used. This is increasingly reflected in transparency provisions across regulatory and normative frameworks. Transparency is a low-bar, high-impact step that can be implemented immediately.

The principle that people affected by crisis have rights to accurate information predates the current AI debate. The Signal Code establishes a human rights foundation from which transparency obligations for AI systems follow (Harvard Humanitarian Initiative, 2017).

In humanitarian contexts, this extends beyond direct interaction with a system. Individuals may never encounter an AI system directly, yet decisions about eligibility, prioritisation, or access to services may be shaped by it. The right to know applies in these cases.

At present, this is not established as a governance requirement in humanitarian AI deployment. Without it, affected populations cannot understand, question, or contest how decisions affecting them are made.

8 Why independent assurance is needed

Internal governance cannot verify itself

An organisation that designs, deploys, and assesses its own AI systems faces the same problem as a company that audits its own accounts. The output may be accurate but without independent oversight, there is no reliable way to tell.

This is why independent assurance exists in other high-stakes domains. Drug safety relies on independent clinical review. Aircraft certification involves regulators and third-party inspectors, not only manufacturers. In each case, credibility depends not only on the rigour of the process, but on the separation between those providing assurance and those whose systems are being assessed. It's also the reason why AI models are evaluated on data sets that are separate from their training data.

The humanitarian sector has its own tradition of thinking about risks from ungoverned experimentation on vulnerable populations. Sandvik, Jacobsen and McDonald (2017) provide the most systematic analysis of humanitarian innovation risks, identifying the absence of accountability and oversight mechanisms as a structural feature of how the sector has historically adopted new technologies, a pattern AI adoption is reproducing at greater speed and scale.

NIST's March 2026 analysis of post-deployment monitoring challenges found that organisations consistently under-invest in monitoring not from lack of intent but because competitive pressure, cost, and administrative burden create structural incentives against it. This finding applies with particular force in a resource-constrained sector, and that confirms why voluntary internal governance alone cannot close the verification gap.

Do we know how to assure models?

A February 2026 expert workshop at Stuart Russell's International Association for Safe and Ethical AI, convened by Fathom and drawing participants from government, industry, civil society, and the assurance community across six countries, stress-tested exactly this approach. Its conclusion was unambiguous: independent verification organisations represent a genuine improvement over both ad hoc voluntary frameworks and traditional prescriptive regulation. The science of evaluation is advanced enough to begin (Averi, 2026). The critical unresolved challenges of post-deployment monitoring methodology, responsibility allocation across complex AI value chains, and enforcement authority are structural and fixable, not technical dead ends.

The humanitarian sector is not waiting for a methodology that doesn't exist. It is waiting for the investment to build one suited to its specific conditions.

Assurance rewards responsible practice

The principles framework established by Floridi et al. (2018) of beneficence, non-maleficence, autonomy, justice, and explicability is widely cited as the ethical foundation for AI governance. Independent assurance is the mechanism through which those principles become verifiable rather than aspirational.

For governance approaches to function as credible standards, there must be a way for them to be assessed, compared, and trusted beyond the organisation applying them. Without this, commitments remain difficult to verify in practice, and distinctions between stronger and weaker governance approaches are hard to sustain.

Public support for aid spending is weak and budgets are being cut precisely as humanitarian caseloads rise. Agencies are adopting AI rapidly to do more with less but adoption without governance creates an unmanaged liability. When a high-profile AI failure occurs, and in current conditions the structural preconditions for one are in place, the agency that deployed a system with independent assurance behind it is in a fundamentally different position from one that did not. The question shifts from ‘Why did you do this?’ to ‘Did you follow the standard?’ That distinction matters acutely when a story is running in the press or a parliamentary committee is asking questions about aid spending. Independent assurance makes adoption politically sustainable in an environment where the sector can least afford a governance scandal.

As AI systems increasingly influence who receives assistance, when, and on what terms, expectations will shift from demonstrating internal compliance to showing that safeguards can be independently verified. Self-assessment, however thorough, will not be sufficient for higher-risk applications indefinitely.

The case for independent humanitarian AI assurance is reinforced by developments in the wider AI governance field. The Partnership on AI *Strengthening the AI Assurance Ecosystem Report* (2026) maps the emerging architecture of third-party AI assurance across sectors, including institutional infrastructure, audit methodologies, and independence requirements. The UK Government’s *DSIT Trusted Third-Party AI Assurance Roadmap* (September 2025) commits £11 million to developing an independent AI assurance profession, including professional standards and competency frameworks in collaboration with the Alan Turing Institute. These developments indicate that structured, independent, third-party assurance for high-stakes AI systems is becoming a baseline expectation across sectors.

Jill Lepore, writing in The New Yorker in March 2026, described Anthropic’s recent release of an AI governance document as marking “a striking transfer of public responsibility from constitutional government to private tech firms” (Jill Lepore, The New Yorker, March 2026). The humanitarian sector is not insulated from that transfer – it is among its most exposed sites.

Limits of upstream assurance

A common assumption in the wider AI governance debate is that auditing at the model level, through requirements placed on major AI developers, will cascade sufficient assurance to downstream users. In humanitarian contexts, this assumption does not hold.

A foundation model assessed as safe for general use may still produce harmful outputs in low-resource languages, conflict settings, or adversarial information environments that upstream testing was not designed to capture. Humanitarian organisations rarely deploy foundation models directly. They deploy applications built on those models, combined with local data, specific workflows, and human processes that no upstream audit reaches.

Upstream auditing is necessary, but it does not resolve the accountability question. The organisation deploying the system remains responsible for its effects, regardless of what assurance the underlying model carries.

Frontier models are therefore already present in humanitarian contexts through individual staff accounts, third-party applications built on foundation models, and supplier-driven updates to existing systems. This is happening without any sector-specific evaluation of their suitability having occurred. No benchmark framework currently exists to assess whether these systems are appropriate for the failure modes that matter most in humanitarian deployment: performance equity across low-resource languages, reliability in conflict-sensitive information environments, or accountability pathways for populations who cannot opt out of systems influencing their access to assistance. Establishing the criteria against which AI systems should be assessed before being considered appropriate for humanitarian deployment is the logical extension of the governance work described in this paper. It shifts accountability upstream, to the point where it can most effectively shape system design, rather than governing consequences after deployment has occurred.

The communities least well-served by current frontier AI models are precisely those humanitarian actors are mandated to reach. Research on multilingual performance in large language models consistently documents severe performance degradation in low-resource languages, including languages widely spoken in crisis-affected contexts such as Arabic dialects, Tigrinya, Dinka, and Nuer, relative to high-resource languages such as English and French (Kumar et al., 2025; Pava et al., 2025). Does any donor or pooled fund grant agreement currently ask whether an AI tool deployed in a humanitarian programme has been evaluated in the languages of the people it serves?

What a humanitarian public good benchmark would test

Most existing AI benchmarks assess capability: how well a model performs on standardised tasks (MMLU, HumanEval), or safety in narrow technical senses, including factual accuracy (TruthfulQA) and resistance to adversarial prompts (red-teaming evaluations). A humanitarian public good benchmark would need to test something different: whether a model can reason reliably under the conditions that actually define humanitarian contexts.

Those conditions include data scarcity, where models must perform without the high-frequency, structured data on which commercial systems are trained. Contested facts, where outputs interact with adversarial information environments rather than stable knowledge bases. Power asymmetries, where the populations affected by outputs have no meaningful ability to challenge or correct them. And decisions with irreversible consequences – access to food, shelter, protection, legal status – for people with no alternative and no recourse.

The conditions identified here are illustrative and help establish the nature of what a humanitarian public good benchmark must address, rather than its full scope. No existing benchmark evaluates these conditions. Establishing the criteria for one is a foundational task of SAFE AI's Phase 2 auditing hub.

What humanitarian AI auditing involves

Independent assurance of humanitarian AI systems requires a methodology built for the conditions of humanitarian deployment, not adapted from general-purpose AI audit frameworks. Four components constitute the core of an audit designed for this context.

1. **Context-specific evaluation.** General model benchmarks test performance on standard tasks. Humanitarian deployment requires evaluation against the failure modes that matter in these specific contexts: performance equity across low-resource languages and language variants spoken by crisis-affected populations; reliability in adversarial

information environments where deliberate manipulation and disinformation are present; and documented analysis of how the system behaves when used for the specific functions – eligibility determination, needs assessment, protection screening, anticipatory action – for which it is being deployed. Testing that does not cover these conditions does not constitute adequate assurance for humanitarian use.

2. **Transparency obligations.** For an audit to be meaningful, the auditor must be able to access training data provenance, documented failure modes, update and change policies, downstream use restrictions, and supply chain disclosure. Where a developer is unable or unwilling to provide this information, the audit cannot proceed and the system cannot be recommended for humanitarian deployment. These disclosure requirements apply to foundation models on which humanitarian applications are built, not only to the applications themselves.
3. **Human oversight architecture by risk tier.** Audit findings must assess whether the governance architecture around the system is proportionate to the risk it carries. Lower-risk applications require documented and auditable internal processes. Higher-risk systems – those influencing eligibility, prioritisation, protection risk analysis, or access to essential services – require evidence that human authorisation is required at each decision point and that autonomous capability cannot be introduced through system updates without renewed assessment and deployer consent.
4. **Community accountability mechanism.** No audit of a humanitarian AI system is complete without assessment of whether affected populations have a meaningful pathway to raise concerns about system outputs, and whether those concerns can result in system adjustment, limitation, or withdrawal. This is the mechanism through which the right to know becomes enforceable rather than aspirational, and through which community-based audit input is integrated into formal governance. Where no such mechanism exists, the audit finding must name its absence.

These four components apply to systems at the point of humanitarian deployment. They also apply upstream, to the assessment of whether foundation models and AI systems are appropriate for humanitarian deployment at all – before they are integrated into humanitarian applications. Establishing sector-specific benchmarks against which AI developers can be assessed before their systems enter humanitarian contexts is the logical extension of this methodology, giving developers a credible pathway to demonstrate that their systems meet the sector's requirements, and giving humanitarian organisations a basis for procurement decisions that goes beyond vendor assurance. It is the direction SAFE AI's Phase 2 auditing hub is designed to pursue.

Value for money and markets signals

Where efficiency pressure drives adoption faster than governance can follow, the risks are structural rather than incidental. Independent research confirms that humanitarian AI adoption is currently driven by individual staff use and funding pressure rather than organisational strategy or governance readiness, with ethics-based procurement proving inadequate as the primary safeguard (Coppi, 2026; Robinson, 2025).

For donors and institutional partners, the risk is straightforward. Without independent verification, AI-enabled programmes carry reputational, operational, and safeguarding exposure that programme design alone cannot mitigate. SAFE AI reduces that exposure by making governance claims testable, enabling comparison across deployments, and allowing investment decisions to be based on evidence rather than assurance alone.

In the absence of shared assurance mechanisms, the humanitarian AI market is likely to evolve in predictable ways. Information asymmetries between vendors and buyers persist. Claims of responsible AI remain difficult to verify. Dependence on proprietary systems

increases. Risk is externalised to affected populations. These are not isolated failures. They are structural features of markets without independent verification and shared standards, as reflected in cross-sector incident tracking efforts. Assurance infrastructure helps correct these distortions by making claims testable, enabling comparability, and aligning incentives with responsible use.

There is also a direct efficiency case. At present, organisations repeat similar assessments across procurement, risk review, and monitoring for comparable systems. This creates duplication, uneven standards, and higher transaction costs, particularly for smaller organisations. A shared sector-level approach allows verification to be conducted once and used by multiple actors, reducing duplication and lowering the cost of governance across the system.

The investment case follows. The cost of the governance gap, in reputational damage, operational disruption, community harm, and downstream liability, consistently exceeds the cost of building proportionate safeguards in advance.

What independent assurance requires

Independent assurance is governance that can be verified. Four conditions define what would be credible assurance in humanitarian AI contexts:

1. **Separation of roles.** Deployment, assessment, and accountability cannot sit within the same organisation. Humanitarian actors cannot credibly verify their own systems.
2. **Access and disclosure.** Assurance depends on access to training data provenance, failure modes, update policies, and upstream model dependencies. Without which, systems cannot be assured.
3. **Context-specific evaluation.** Systems must be tested against humanitarian conditions: low-resource languages, adversarial information environments, and the specific functions they perform (e.g. eligibility, protection, targeting).
4. **Community accountability mechanisms.** Affected populations must be able to identify harms, challenge outputs, and trigger review or withdraw.

These conditions apply both at deployment and upstream, including decisions about whether systems are appropriate for humanitarian use at all

Implications for humanitarian AI governance

These requirements change how humanitarian AI is governed in practice:

- **Governance moves to sector level.** Verification cannot be produced by individual organisations. It requires shared infrastructure that others can rely on.
- **Procurement becomes decisive.** Systems that cannot be audited or disclosed cannot be used. Governance is set at the point of purchase.
- **Upstream systems come into scope.** Foundation models and third-party systems are part of the governance boundary, not external to it.
- **Assurance shapes incentives.** Without it, the sector relies on vendor claims and becomes dependent on systems it cannot evaluate. With it, transparency and verifiability become conditions for adoption.
- **Participation becomes enforceable.** Community input is required to identify harms and influence system use, not treated as consultation.

Humanitarian AI governance shifts from internal oversight to shared, verifiable infrastructure.

9 What next?

The right to know that an AI system is being used and is influencing decisions that affect you is a minimum requirement. Without transparency, other accountability mechanisms cannot function in practice. The SAFE AI Framework's deployment-level tools are designed on that basis.

The SAFE AI Framework, forthcoming May 2026, operationalises AI governance at deployment level for organisations. It provides tools for involving communities affected by crises, role-specific guidance for teams, decision gates, documentation requirements, and accountability mechanisms. This is what organisations can act on now.

Independent humanitarian AI assurance is what follows. Building the infrastructure for scrutiny which is adequately resourced, structurally separate from the organisations deploying AI, and capable of verifying claims rather than only receiving them is the governance task the sector must now invest in completing. Defining what AI developers should be required to demonstrate before their systems enter humanitarian contexts is required through sector-specific benchmarks that shift accountability upstream to where it can most effectively shape system design.

Four distinct reasons to invest in independent humanitarian AI assurance

They address different audiences and converge on the same architecture.

The first is about enabling innovation. The humanitarian sector is not short of interest in AI staff are already experimenting, often without knowing whether what they are doing is sanctioned. The barrier to adoption at scale is the absence of a shared framework that gives confidence that using a particular tool in a particular way is considered and defensible. Governance infrastructure resolves that. A sector standard gives people permission to act rather than reasons to stall. It also determines how well organisations are positioned for what comes next. Those that have built governance scaffolding now will be able to assess and integrate new AI capabilities, including agentic systems moving rapidly toward operational deployment, within a framework that already exists. Those that have not will face a starker choice when the next development arrives: adopt without any basis for doing so, or pause and fall further behind. The external pressure compounds this. A sector that cannot demonstrate accountability for its AI deployments will face restriction from donors tightening compliance requirements, from parliamentary scrutiny of aid spending, and from public pressure in a funding environment already hostile to waste and opacity. Left unaddressed, the governance gap will be used to shut adoption down.

The second is to share the risk. No agency should carry sole accountability for high-stakes AI deployment in humanitarian contexts. Independent assurance distributes that accountability across a sector-wide architecture. The agency that participates has a credible answer when something goes wrong. The question shifts from 'Why did you do this?' to 'Did you follow the standard?' That distinction matters most at the moment of failure, which is precisely the moment the sector can least afford to be without it.

The third is to relieve political pressure. Aid spending is under sustained public and parliamentary scrutiny in most major donor countries. That scrutiny now lands in a context that has shifted materially. The concentration of AI capability in a small number of technology companies, and the growing visibility of those companies' proximity to

political power, when multilateral humanitarian commitments are under pressure and conflict environments are intensifying, has made questions about whose infrastructure humanitarian organisations depend on both more salient and more urgent. These are companies whose models humanitarian workers are already using in contexts where the politics of humanitarian access are anything but stable. Taxpayers and parliamentarians in donor countries, already sceptical about aid effectiveness, now have an additional line of questioning available. A sector that cannot answer questions about its own AI governance and about its relationship to the companies providing it is exposed on two fronts simultaneously.

The sector has a narrow window to respond. After a scandal, the narrative belongs to the sceptics. The inaugural Global Dialogue on AI Governance convenes in Geneva in July 2026, immediately following the SAFE AI launch. How accountability for AI affecting the world's most vulnerable will be a question in that room, asked by governments answerable to their own publics. The sector should be ready with more than principles.

Fourth is the sector's stated commitments to localisation and participation. Community-in-the-loop governance, localisation, and the redistribution of power toward locally-led organisations and affected communities have been explicit sector commitments for over a decade, but resistant to delivery through argument alone. Architecture could deliver what persuasion has not (Costanza-Chock, 2020; Madianou, 2019). If AI capability tracks funding and it will, because large agencies can afford proprietary systems and smaller local actors cannot, the humanitarian AI landscape will mirror and amplify the existing power asymmetry. Shared infrastructure and independent assurance are the only structural counterweights available.

No one has yet asked, on behalf of affected populations, what humanitarian AI is for, who approved its use, or against what standard that approval was made.

This creates a clear opportunity for donor leadership. A multi-donor compact anchoring AI governance requirements to humanitarian programming would shift market incentives and translate standards into conditions for use. The governance principles are there. The framework is arriving. Implementation is what makes it real.

A SAFE AI governance companion paper forthcoming provides a structured overview of AI governance frameworks, laws, and standards, and how they relate to humanitarian action (April 2026)

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The SAFE (Standards and Assurance Framework for Ethical) AI project is a collaboration between CDAC Network, The Alan Turing Institute and Humanitarian AI Advisory.

cdacnetwork.org/safe-ai

CDAC Network is the global alliance of organisations – including UN agencies, the Red Cross/Red Crescent Movement, local and international NGOs, media development and specialist communications entities – working to ensure people can access safe, trustworthy information and communicate during crises.

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